

The potential for artificial intelligence (AI) to help with better prescribing and medicines optimisation

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Medicines do a lot of good

**Effective treatment of
acute conditions**

**Primary care secondary
prevention of
cardiovascular disease**

**Effective management of
long term conditions**

But sometimes medicines do more harm than good

Overprescribing – the use of a medicine where there is a better non-medicine alternative, or the use is inappropriate for that patients' circumstances and wishes.

Prescribing in primary care has increased over time

Taking multiple medicines (**polypharmacy**) can do more harm than good (**problematic polypharmacy**)

The risks of not addressing problematic polypharmacy include:

- Increased risk of medication error and associated harm
- Increased risk of hospital admissions
- Increased risk of non-adherence (reduced effectiveness)
- Waste (economic and environmental impact)

Particular concerns with polypharmacy with MLTCs include:

- 'Overtreatment' leading to harm
- Therapeutic cascade: using medication to treat the side effects of other medications
- The 'treatment burden' for patients and carers; could medication regimes be simplified?
- Use of medicines where risk of harm is likely to outweigh any benefits

Medicines optimisation quality standard (NICE)

- One quarter of the population has a long-term condition
- One quarter of people over 60 have two or more long-term conditions
- With an ageing population, the use of multiple medicines (known as polypharmacy) is increasing
- Between 30-50% of medicines prescribed for long-term conditions are not taken as intended
- [NICE medicines optimisation: quality standard](#)

What is medicines optimisation?

Definition:

Person-centred approach to safe and effective medicines use, to ensure people obtain the best possible outcomes from their medicines. Medicines optimisation applies to people who may or may not take their medicines effectively.

Shared decision-making is an essential part of evidence-based medicine, seeking to use the best available evidence to guide decisions about the care of the individual patient, taking into account their needs, preferences and values'

[NICE guideline: Medicines optimisation: the safe and effective use of medicines to enable the best possible outcomes](#)

Preventing and addressing overprescribing

20 recommendations to tackle overprescribing

Department
of Health &
Social Care

Good for you, good for us, good for everybody

A plan to reduce overprescribing to make patient care better and safer, support the NHS, and reduce carbon emissions

Published 22 September 2021

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-overprescribing-review-report>

Preventing and addressing overprescribing

AIM: To achieve long term sustainable reductions to overprescribing via delivery of systemic and cultural improvements within the NHS

Objectives	1. Work with patients, carers and the system to tackle overprescribing	2. Improve and implement prescribing processes, reviews and guidance	3. Utilise digital technologies to address overprescribing	4. Improve data for feedback to clinicians and commissioners to guide prioritisation and monitor success	5. Update training and development to reflect the growing understanding of overprescribing	6. Assess and support system action to address the carbon impact of unnecessary prescribing and medicines waste	7. Strengthen the evidence base for overprescribing and enhance the process of getting evidence into practice

EVALUATION FRAMEWORK: Effectively measure and monitor programme impact

Address health inequalities

How might AI help improve prescribing and medicines optimisation for patients with multiple long term conditions?

- Reducing medication error: decision support when considering whether to prescribe a medication
- Collation of information when undertaking a medication review
- Decision support when reviewing a patient's medicines, including identifying potential overprescribing
- Identifying patients who may need additional support with their medicines

Reducing medication error: decision support when considering whether to prescribe a medication

‘Key use cases for artificial intelligence to reduce the frequency of adverse drug events: a scoping review’

- 78 heterogeneous articles using a range of AI techniques and a wide range of medications and adverse drug events (ADEs)
- Several key case studies suggested AI could contribute to reduction in frequency and consequences of ADEs
- Most (94%) studies assessed technical algorithm performance with few testing AI in clinical settings
- 74% of articles published in the last 5 years

[Reference: https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500\(21\)00229-6/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/article/PIIS2589-7500(21)00229-6/fulltext)

Collation of information when undertaking a medication review

- What are the examples of non-AI approaches?
- Could AI do better?

Collation of information for medication review

CVAMP Repeat Prescription request

Check QoF alerts to see which questionnaires to send to patient

- Heart Failure - HF007 - Record a heart failure and medication review
- Dementia - DEM004 - Record review of care within last 12 months

Has the patient already recently returned the questionnaire

Select preset for questionnaire - can send multiple

Questionnaire...

Average home BP (if recorded)

Common Measurements

Quick Glance Template Overview

BP	106/58 mmHg - (14.13/7.73 kPa)	12 Apr 2022	
Pulse rate	78 bpm	12 Apr 2022	(8)
Pulse rhythm	O/E - pulse rhythm regular (2431.)	28 Jan 2022	(8)
BMI	15.94 Kg/m ²	19 Oct 2022	(21)
Weight	40.8 Kg (6 st 6 lb)	19 Oct 2022	(25)
Height	1.6 m (5' 3")	12 Apr 2022	(16)
Alcohol intake	0 Units/Week	29 Mar 2021	(6)
Smoking Status	Ex-smoker (Ub1na)	26 Aug 2021	(22)

Calculate BMI press here

BMI

Outstanding Recalls

Last BT results

Readings of Serum creatinine level

Serum creatinine level	79 umol/L	17 Nov 2021
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Readings of Haemoglobin A1c level

Haemoglobin A1c level - IFCC standardised	39 mmol/mol	17 Nov 2021
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Readings of Serum alkaline phosphatase level

Serum alkaline phosphatase level	74 iu/L	17 Nov 2021
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Readings of Haemoglobin concentration

Haemoglobin concentration	138 g/L	17 Nov 2021
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Readings of Serum TSH level

Serum TSH level	1.5 miu/L	17 Nov 2021
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Readings of Serum cholesterol level

Serum cholesterol level	6.6 mmol/L	03 Dec 2014
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Click here to request a Blood test & make a BT appt

ICE req...

BT appt

Prompts for structured medication review

F12 Structured Medication Review

Other Details... Exact date & time Tue 08 Nov 2022 09:14

Changing the consultation date will affect all other data entered. To avoid this, cancel and press the 'Next' button [Hide Warning](#)

Medication Medication Optimisation

F12 Structured Medication Review

Step 1

1 - Check History / Reviews / Bloods etc Prev Reviews PMH DOT Recall BP & bloods

Review alerts 2 - Check SAFETY Guidance (inc QOF QI) **IIF** SAFETY/NSAID / IIF Alert

Record QOF med review 3 - Check STOPP Guidance STOPP

4 - Check Anticholinergic Burden Check ACB (if >3)

5 - Check High Risk Meds High Risk Medication

6 - Record QOF Full Review & Alerts Med Review QOF QOF Alerts

7 - Reauthorise Medication Reauthorise Meds

Step 2

Current Medication & Allergies Full Repeat Medication Node LTC / Drug Monitoring Req

Current Repeat Medication

Medication	Date	Strength	Frequency	Notes
Furosemide 40mg tablets	20 Oct 2022	ONE to ...	28 tablet	
Macrogol compound oral powder sachets ...	20 Oct 2022	Take th...	30 sachet	-
Paracetamol 250mg/5ml oral suspension ...	31 Oct 2022	Take tw...	400 ml	-
Zerobase 11% cream (Thornton & Ross Ltd)	20 Oct 2022	Moderat...	500 gram	-
Aymes Shake powder 57g sachets (Flavou...	20 Oct 2022	1 To be ...	56 sachet	+

Current Acute Medication

Acute medication in last 6 months

All Read Coded Allergies

28 Jun 2016 Amitriptyline adverse reaction (Xa5JE)

All Drug Sensitivities

Structured Med Review (Lvl 3) (Initial or follow ups) Limited review undertaken due to COVID situation

DOAC Review Shared decision making

Record Optimisation Notes / Actions / Activities

Update Medication Review Date (QOF)

Encounter

DRUM

PCN DES Reporting

Reporting Method	QOF
<input type="checkbox"/> Med review by clinical pharmacist (updates QOF)	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Med review done by pharmacy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Seen by clinical pharmacist	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Seen by clinical pharmacist in care home	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Seen by pharmacy technician	<input type="checkbox"/>

Non PCN DES Reporting

Reporting Method	QOF
<input type="checkbox"/> Med Review done by CCG pharmacist (update...)	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Seen by pharmacist	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Care home visit	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Med Review done by CCG technician	<input type="checkbox"/>

Review Toolkit

- Quick Review Tips
- Med Rvw guide
- QT Meds
- APC meds / falls risk
- Elderly / Frailty (new)
- QRISK2
- CHADSVASc
- 6 CIT
- Mental Health

Creatinine Clearance IIF

- Current CRCL & issues
- Calculate CRCL
- ICE
- View Lab Results

Weight Kg

Malnutrition

- MUST Score Calculator

BP & Obs

BP mmHg

- Core Health Obs

Recalls & Appts

- Recalls
- Appts

Tasks

- GP Actions Request
- GP Reauthorise Req
- Admin Action Req
- Pharmacy Rev Req

Other F12 Templates

- F12 Data Templates

New Letter to pt

- New Letter

Updated 21.03.22

Show recordings from other templates

Show empty recordings

Information Print Suspend Ok Cancel Show Incomplete Fields

Could AI do better?

- It's a big ask!
- Need to recognise the conditions that the patient has and the medication they are taking and then pull together the information that might help with a medication review, including identifying potential missing information
- Could AI do this in a reliable way, and provide health care professionals with the source of any guidance, e.g. NICE?

Decision support when reviewing a patient's medicines, including identifying potential overprescribing

- Reviewing medicines of patients with multiple long term conditions with polypharmacy is complex
- Decision support tools are available but there are limitations
- Could AI do better?
- Big ask, potentially requiring interrogation of NHS and other databases to advise on likely benefits/risks of each patient's medicines

Identifying patients who may need additional support with their medicines

- Adherence problems, difficulties with managing medicines and (potential) waste are important problems for the health service
- Could AI identify patterns to pick up patients who may need additional support with their medicines?
- Factors that could be considered include medication possession ratio, poor apparent response to treatment, polypharmacy, demographic factors, but talking to patients/observing patients may be most effective!

Summary

While medicines can do a lot of good, they can also be harmful, particularly when overprescribed.

AI has potential to help with better prescribing and medicines optimisation, including:

- Reducing medication error through decision support when considering whether to prescribe a medication
- Collation of information when undertaking a medication review
- Decision support when reviewing a patient's medicines, including identifying potential overprescribing
- Identifying patients who may need additional support with their medicines

